

SYNTHESIS OF NEW LOCAL ANAESTHETICS

BY P. N. BHARGAVA AND M. G. RAGHVAN NAIR

Piperidino- and diethylamino-acetyl-1-aminoanthraquinones, piperidino- and diethylamino-acetyl-2-aminofluorenes, and 3-amino-4-piperidino- and 3-amino-4-diethylamino-acetamidoanisols as well as their hydrochlorides have been synthesised, and their local anaesthetic activity tested.

Previous workers have proved that the essential structural requirements for a local anaesthetic are a lipolytic end containing an aromatic nucleus, a hydrophylic end consisting of a tertiary amino group, and an intermediate alkyl or substituted alkyl chain. Compounds having dialkylamino-alkylamino group connected to an aromatic or heterocyclic nucleus as the lipolytic moiety confer greater activity and less toxicity than the benzene analogues (Gupta, Shah and Gaiind, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 845; Blicke and Parke, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1200; Mattocks and Hutchinson, *ibid.*, 1948 70, 3474; Sargrevskaya and Neovadba, *J. Gen. Chem. U. S. S. R.*, 1938, 8, 924).

Considering these facts, 1-aminoanthraquinone, 2-aminofluorene and 3-nitro-4-aminoanisol were taken as the starting primary amines which were condensed in the first stage with chloroacetyl chloride to obtain the corresponding chloroacetylamino compounds. These were further condensed with secondary amines, like piperidine and diethylamine. The nitro group present in 3-nitro-4-piperidinoacetamidoanisol and 3-nitro-4-diethylaminoacetamidoanisol was carefully reduced to amino group. The hydrochlorides of these bases have been prepared and their local anaesthetic activity tested.

The dihydrochlorides of 3-amino-4-piperidino- and 4-diethylamino acetamido-anisols have been found to be successful local anaesthetics. The hydrochlorides of piperidinoacetyl-1-aminoanthraquinone and diethylaminoacetyl-1-aminoanthraquinone produced only incomplete anaesthesia on rabbit's cornea. The 2-aminofluorene derivatives have been found to have a weak local anaesthetic action.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chloroacetyl-1-aminoanthraquinone.—Chloroacetyl chloride (3 c.c.), dissolved in pure benzene (12 c.c.), was gradually added to 1-aminoanthraquinone (5 g.), dissolved in benzene (30 c.c.). The reaction mixture was warmed at 70° on a water-bath for 1½ hours. Benzene was then distilled off and the residue washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and then dried. The product was recrystallised from alcohol in pale yellow crystals, m. p. 212°. (Found: N, 4.39; Cl, 11.79. $C_{16}H_{10}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.67; Cl, 11.85%).

Piperidinoacetyl-1-aminoanthraquinone.—To chloroacetyl-1-aminoanthraquinone (5 g.), dissolved in absolute alcohol (50 c.c.), piperidine (5 c.c.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 4 to 5 hours. Alcohol and excess of piperidine were recovered by distillation and the residue washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The product was crystallised from 80% alcohol and recrystallised from benzene in bright yellow crystals, m. p. 235°. (Found: N, 7.84. $C_{21}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8.04%).

The *hydrochloride* was prepared by dissolving the base (2 g.) in dry ether (20 c.c.) and saturating the solution with dry HCl gas. Ether was decanted off and the semi-solid mass was recrystallised from absolute alcohol, m. p. 320°. (Found: N, 7.14; Cl, 9.18. $C_{21}H_{21}O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 7.28; Cl, 9.23%).

Diethylaminoacetyl-1-aminoanthraquinone.—It was likewise prepared and crystallised from benzene in glistening, brownish yellow plates, m. p. 164°. (Found: N, 8.12. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.33%).

The *hydrochloride* was crystallised from absolute alcohol, m. p. 256°. (Found: N, 7.42; Cl, 9.39. $C_{20}H_{21}O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 7.51; Cl, 9.53%).

Chloroacetyl-2-aminofluorene.—To 2-aminofluorene (5 g.), dissolved in benzene (30 c.c.), chloroacetyl chloride (5 c.c.), dissolved in the same solvent (20 c.c.), was gradually added with constant shaking, and warmed on a water-bath for 1½ hours at 65°. Benzene was then distilled off and the residue washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and then dried. The product was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 172°. (Found: N, 5.39; Cl, 10.86. $C_{15}H_{12}ONCl$ requires N, 5.44; Cl, 10.95%).

Piperidinoacetyl-2-aminofluorene, prepared similarly as above, was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 145°. (Found: N, 9.08. $C_{20}H_{22}ON_2$ requires N, 9.16%).

The *hydrochloride* was crystallised from absolute alcohol, m. p. 221°. (Found: N, 8.08; Cl, 10.27. $C_{20}H_{23}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 8.18; Cl, 10.36%).

Diethylaminoacetyl-2-aminofluorene was similarly prepared and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 85°. (Found: N, 9.43. $C_{10}H_{22}ON_2$ requires N, 9.53%).

The *hydrochloride* was crystallised from absolute alcohol, m. p. 196°. (Found: N, 8.39; Cl, 10.71. $C_{19}H_{23}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 8.47; Cl, 10.74%).

3-Nitro-4-chloroacetamidobenzol.—3-Nitro-4-aminobenzol (2 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (20 c.c.) and a solution of chloroacetyl chloride (1.4 c.c.) in dry benzene (15 c.c.) was added to it gradually during 10 minutes at 15°. The mixture was refluxed gently on a water-bath for 2 hours and then cooled. The greenish yellow precipitate after recovery of the solvent was washed several times with water, dried and crystallised from alcohol in greenish yellow plates, m. p. 101°. (Found: N, 11.36; Cl, 14.48. $C_7H_6O_4N_2Cl$ requires N, 11.45; Cl, 14.52%).

3-Nitro-4-piperidinoacetamidobenzol.—Piperidine (2 c.c.) was added to the above compound (2 g.), dissolved in absolute alcohol (30 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed gently on a water-bath for 5 hours. The alcohol was recovered and the semisolid mass was cooled, when yellow needles separated. The product was then washed several times with water, dried and crystallised from absolute alcohol, m. p. 130°. (Found: N, 14.26. $C_{14}H_{19}O_4N_3$ requires N, 14.33%).

3-Amino-4-piperidinoacetamidobenzol.—The preceding compound (2 g.), dissolved in 70% acetic acid (30 c.c.), was reduced with zinc dust (14 g.), added in small quantities at a time, keeping the mixture cooled in water so that the temperature did not rise above 40°. After addition of the whole of zinc dust, the mixture was gently heated on a water-bath at 60° for 3 to 4 hours, and filtered. The filtrate was cooled in ice and to this ammonium chloride (20 g.) was added. The solution was made

alkaline with ammonia and the base extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether recovered. The product, thus obtained, was recrystallised from alcohol in brownish yellow plates, m. p. 122. (Found : N, 15.86. $C_{14}H_{21}O_2N_3$ requires N, 15.97%).

The *dihydrochloride* was crystallised from absolute alcohol in brown plates, m. p. 212. (Found : N, 12.43 ; Cl, 21.01. $C_{14}H_{23}O_2N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 12.5 ; Cl, 21.13%).

3-Amino-4-diethylaminoacetamidoanisol was similarly prepared as above and obtained as reddish brown needles, m. p. 58°. (Found : N, 16.71. $C_{13}H_{21}O_2N_3$ requires N, 16.75%).

The *dihydrochloride* was crystallised from absolute alcohol in brown needles, m. p. 175. (Found : N, 12.85 ; Cl, 21.82. $C_{13}H_{23}O_2N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 12.96 ; Cl, 21.92%).

The above hydrochlorides were tested for their local anaesthetic activity on rabbit's cornea. Each substance was used in 2% solution and compared with procaine hydrochloride solution of the same strength. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Hydrochloride of:	Time for onset of anaesthesia (complete loss of reflex action).	Duration for which complete loss of reflex action lasted.
Piperidinoacetyl-1-aminoanthraquinone	Never complete (1.5 min.)	Incomplete anaesthesia for 31 min. (40 min.)
Diethylaminoacetyl- do	Incomplete (2 min.)	Incomplete for 32 min. (38 min.)
Piperidinoacetyl-2-aminofluorene	4 min. (1.25 min.)	22 min. (39 min.)
Diethylaminoacetyl- do	3.5 min (1 min.)	24 min. (40 min.)
* 3-Amino-4-piperidino-acetamidoanisol	2 min. (1.25 min.)	36 min. (39 min.)
3-Amino-4-diethylamino- do	1.5 min (1.5 min.)	41 min. (40 min.)

* refers to dihydrochlorides.

The value for standard substance are shown in parenthesis (here procaine hydrochloride was used as a standard substance).

Thanks are due to the authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for providing necessary facilities.

ORGANIC CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY, BANARAS.

Received May 25, 1966.